

Nitrido- and Imido - or Nitrene Complexes of Molybdenum

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The molybdenum(VI) nitrido-complexes $[\text{MoNCl}_4\text{L}_2]$ [$\text{L}_2 = \text{dipyridyl}$, or $(\text{Ph}_2\text{PO})_2$], $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{MoNCl}_5]$ and $[\text{MoN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_3]$ [$\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}_2$, Et_2 , or $(\text{CH}_2)_5$] are prepared by addition of the appropriate ligand to solutions of a molybdenum(VI) nitrido-species formed from $[\text{MoCl}_4\text{L}_2]$ [$\text{L} = \text{tetrahydrofuran}$ (thf), or MeCN] and trimethylsilylazide (tmsa). The complexes $[\text{MoN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_3]$ can also be prepared from $[\text{MoCl}_4(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2]$ and sodium azide in methyl cyanide under reflux. The molybdenum(V) nitrido-complexes, $[\text{MoNCl}_3\text{L}_2]$ [$\text{L}_2 = \text{dipyridyl}$, $(\text{PPh}_3)_2$, or $(\text{PPh}_2\text{Me})_2$], are prepared analogously from $[\text{MoCl}_4(\text{thf})_2]$ and tmsa. Reaction of $[\text{Mo}(\text{N}_2)_2(\text{dppe})_2]$ ($\text{dppe} = \text{Ph}_2\text{PCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{PPh}_2$) with tmsa in thf under reflux gives the molybdenum(IV) azido-nitrido complex, $[\text{MoN}(\text{N}_2)(\text{dppe})_2]$, which reacts with halogen acids (HX) to give the imido-complexes, $[\text{MoX}_2(\text{NH})(\text{dppe})_2]$. These can be dehydrohalogenated with triethylamine to the molybdenum(IV) nitrido-complexes, $[\text{MoNX}(\text{dppe})_2]$.

NITRIDO-molybdenum moieties are plausible intermediates in the enzymatic nitrogen fixation process and the chemistry of molybdenum nitrido-complexes, particularly the reactivity of the nitride ligand to protonation, is of considerable interest and relevance to studies of nitrogen fixation.

Nitrido-complexes of rhenium(V) have been prepared both from $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ and hydrazine dihydrochloride¹ and from the reaction of halidorhenium(III) complexes with sodium azide.² The degradation of intermediate azido-complexes has also been utilised in the preparation of ruthenium and osmium nitrido-complexes.³

Attempts to prepare molybdenum nitrido complexes by reactions of oxo-complexes such as $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{PMe}_2\text{Ph})_3]$ ⁴ or $[\text{MoOCl}_3(\text{dppe})]$ ⁵ with hydrazines gave only intractable products. The preparation of MoNCl_3 from MoCl_5 and chlorine azide has been reported,⁶ together with some poorly defined adducts. An X-ray crystal structure⁷ has shown MoNCl_3 to be tetrameric in the solid state with Mo-N-Mo bridges. In addition to the inherent dangers of using chlorine azide, the reaction proceeds heterogeneously and the product is difficult to purify. Tetraethylammonium azide has also been utilised to prepare complexes formulated as $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{MoNCl}_4]$ ⁸ by reaction with MoCl_5 in chloroform. However tetraalkylammonium salts are notoriously difficult to render anhydrous and the nitrido-complex appears to be contaminated with an oxo-species, as the ir band at 960 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$, is in fact due to $\nu(\text{Mo}=\text{O})$.⁹

We now report the full details of the preparation (reported briefly¹⁰) of molybdenum nitrido-complexes by reaction of molybdenum halido-precursors with trimethylsilylazide (tmsa). The complex $[\text{MoCl}_4(\text{thf})_2]$ reacts immediately with tmsa in thf or dichloromethane at room temperature to evolve dinitrogen and give a clear orange solution of a molybdenum(VI) nitrido-species (A), but only orange-red oils with rather broad

ir bands assignable to $\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$ could be isolated on removal of the solvent. Nevertheless this product (A) can be used to prepare a range of molybdenum(VI) nitrido-complexes. Their reactions and preparations are summarised in Scheme I, the Roman numerals corresponding to those given in the Table, which summarises analytical and spectroscopic data for the compounds.

(Reaction solvent is in parentheses)
Scheme I.

Molybdenum(VI) nitrido-complexes

Addition of an excess of dry tetraethylammonium chloride to a dichloromethane solution of (A) precipitates yellow crystalline $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{MoNCl}_5]$ (III) which shows $\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$ as a strong ir band at 1032 cm^{-1} . This salt is extremely sensitive to moisture and rapidly decomposes, even in the solid state, in air. The complex $[\text{MoNCl}_3(\text{dppe})]$ (II) is best prepared from (A) and dipyridyl (dpy) in about equivalent amount in MeCN as solvent. It is isolated as a brown, reasonably air-stable solid with $\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$ assigned to an ir band at 1009 cm^{-1} . Reaction of (A) with pyridine or an excess of dipyridyl produces impure products with broad ir bands at about 950 cm^{-1} possibly due to $\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N}$. Addition of two equivalents of triphenylphosphine oxide to (A) in benzene solution causes $[\text{MoNCl}_3(\text{OPPh}_3)_2]$ (I) to crystallise out as pale yellow crystals with $\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$ at 1038 cm^{-1} .

Solutions of (A) are very sensitive to moisture, and since the sodium salts of dithiocarbamates are difficult to dehydrate, their addition to methyl cyanide solutions of (A) causes decomposition. However, trimethylsilyl dithiocarbamates are a convenient source of anhydrous dithiocarbamate-ligands and addition of three equivalents of $\text{Me}_3\text{SiS}_2\text{CNET}_2$ to dichloromethane solutions of (A) give the yellow complex $[\text{MoN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_3]$ (V). Nevertheless the tris (dithiocarbamato) nitrido-complexes are more conveniently prepared in about 60% overall yield by reactions of sodium azide with the complexes $[\text{MoCl}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_3]$ $\text{R}_2 = \text{Me}_2, \text{Et}_2, (\text{CH}_3)_2$. These are derived from $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2]$ as indicated in Scheme 2. The complexes $[\text{MoN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_3]$ are

(Reaction solvent is in parentheses)

Scheme 2

diamagnetic, and stable to air and to moisture even in solution. A strong ir band at about 1020 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$ and ^1H nmr spectra show that the complexes are fluxional in solution, the temperature at which the alkyl groups of the dithiocarbamate become equivalent being a complex function of solvent. Full details of the variable ^1H nmr studies of these and related tris (dithiocarbamato) complexes are to be reported in a subsequent publication.

An X-ray crystal structure of $[\text{MoN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_3]$ ¹¹ confirms that its structure is analogous to that of $[\text{Mo}(\text{NO})(\text{S}_2\text{CNBu}^n)_3]$ ¹² with pentagonal bipyramidal co-ordination of the molybdenum. The Mo-N bond length of $1.62\text{ \AA}$ is similar to that found in $[\text{OsNCl}_5]^{2-}$ ¹³ and $[\text{ReN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNET}_2)_3]$ ¹⁴ (1.61 and $1.66\text{ \AA}$ respectively).

An ochre yellow, very air-sensitive solid, with an ir spectrum similar to that reported for $[\text{MoNCl}_3]_4$ results from heating MoCl_5 with one equivalent of *tmsa* under reflux in CCl_4 . However the product, as that from ClN_3 , is difficult to purify except in very low yield by sublimation, and solutions of (A) are a more convenient starting point for the synthesis of nitrido-complexes. A yellow solid with spectroscopic properties corresponding to those reported for WNCI_5 can be prepared from WCl_6 and *tmsa* in carbon tetrachloride under reflux, but attempts to prepare well defined nitrido-complexes from this have so far been unsuccessful.

Molybdenum (V) nitrido-complexes

Triphenylphosphine reacts with a dichloromethane solution of (A) to give the yellow, crystalline, air-stable molybdenum (V) complex $[\text{MoNCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ (VII), the triphenylphosphine functioning also as a reducing agent. Complex (VII) and other molybdenum(V) nitrides can also be prepared from $[\text{MoCl}_5(\text{thf})_3]$ and *tmsa* as indi-

cated in Scheme 3, via an uncharacterised molybdenum(V) nitride intermediate (B). The methyl-diphenylphosphine analogue (VIII) of $[\text{MoNCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ can be prepared by addition of 2.5 equivalents of methyl-diphenylphosphine to thf solutions of (B). If more basic phosphines such as dimethylphenylphosphine are used, yellow products with strong ir bands at about 1120 cm^{-1} characteristic of the $\text{M}-\text{N}=\text{PR}_3$ grouping are formed. Attempts to purify these phosphinimine complexes lead to decomposition, recrystallisation from hydroxylic solvents giving $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{PMe}_2\text{Ph})_3]$. These phosphinimine derivatives appear to be much less stable than the recently reported ruthenium and osmium complexes $[\text{MCl}_3(\text{NPR}_3)(\text{PR}_3)_2]$ ⁸. It appears that the nitride

* $\text{R}_3 = \text{Ph}_3$ or MePh_2

(Reaction solvent is in parentheses)

Scheme 3

ligand in the chloro-nitrido molybdenum (V) complexes has electrophilic character, which is in direct contrast to its highly nucleophilic properties in the complexes, $[\text{MoN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_3]$. The reactions of co-ordinated nitride ligands with electrophilic reagents to produce *inter alia* thionitrosyl and imido-complexes will be discussed elsewhere.

The complex $[\text{MoNCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ (VII) is paramagnetic, with a magnetic moment of 1.52 B.M. and a well defined epr spectrum in dichloromethane solution at room temperature (Figure). The triplet is attributed to splitting by two equivalent phosphorus nuclei (hyperfine constant 24.5G) and the weaker satellites to molybdenum isotopes with spin $I = \frac{5}{2}$ (hyperfine constant 49G) with the phosphorus splitting superimposed. In contrast to the recently reported epr spectrum of $[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{dppe})]$ ¹⁵ there is no evidence for hyperfine interaction with the chloride ligands. Only very broad signals were observed when powdered samples or dichloromethane glasses were run at about -110°K .

Figure: E. p. r. spectrum of $[\text{MoNCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ in CH_2Cl_2 at 2930 K

The stick diagram shows the interpretation of the spectrum. Triplet 'a' results from superhyperfine interaction between the unpaired electron and two equivalent ^{31}P nuclei ($I = \frac{3}{2}$); this is given by the 75% of Mo nuclei with no nuclear spin. The six triplets illustrated by 'b' and 'c' show additional hyperfine coupling to the 25% of Mo nuclei with $I = \frac{5}{2}$.

The e. p. r. measurements were made at a microwave frequency of 9.131 GHz and a microwave power of 1 mW. Field modulation was 0.2 mT at 100 KHz. The arrow gives the field for the resonance of the diphenylpicrylhydrazyl radical ($g = 2.003$).

Molybdenum(IV) azido nitrido-complex

Both dinitrogen ligands of $\text{trans}[\text{Mo}(\text{N}_2)_2(\text{dppe})_2]$ are lost on reaction with *tmsa* in refluxing thf or methyl cyanide with formation of about 3 moles of dinitrogen and $[\text{MoN}(\text{N}_3)(\text{dppe})_2]$ (IX) in 40–50% yield. It crystallises from methyl cyanide as an air-stable, yellow diamagnetic solid with ir bands at 972 and 2025 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{N}_3)$ respectively. A second product, soluble in diethyl ether, is formed; spectroscopic measurements indicate that it contains azide and Me_3Si groups but attempts to purify this species have so far been unsuccessful. The mechanism of formation of (IX) is unknown, but it cannot be analogous to that of the molybdenum(V) nitrido-complexes, where elimination of trimethylsilyl chloride is involved. Trimethyltin azide also reacts with the bis(dinitrogen) complex to form complex (IX), and again a second product could not be purified or characterised.

Molybdenum(IV) imido- and nitrido-complexes

A suspension of $[\text{MoN}(\text{N}_3)(\text{dppe})_2]$ in methanol reacts rapidly at room temperature with concentrated aqueous hydrohalic acid (HX, X = Cl or Br) to give the pink-purple imido-complexes $[\text{MoX}_2(\text{NH})(\text{dppe})_2]$ (XII) and (XIII), as shown in Scheme 4. No dinitrogen or ammonia is evolved in this reaction, so the imido- (or nitrene) ligand does not originate from the azido-ligand, which is presumably liberated as HN_3 ; it must arise from protonation of the nitrido-ligand.

Imido (NH) complexes have been proposed as reactive intermediates in the acid catalysed decomposition of

the pentaammineazido-complexes of ruthenium and iridium, and in the case of iridium they were trapped out as ligating NH_4SO_3 using sulphate ion.¹⁷ A number of polynuclear complexes of uncertain structure, which may contain bridging NH ligands have also been reported.¹⁸ Organoimido-complexes have been prepared by a number of routes,¹⁹ but the complexes of the type $[\text{MoX}_2(\text{NH})(\text{dppe})_2]$ we believe represent the first examples of well characterised mononuclear complexes of the parent nitrene or imido-ligand.

Complexes (XII) and (XIII) have no ir bands assignable to $\nu(\text{NH})$ or peaks due to the N-H proton in their ^1H nmr spectra, even taken in carefully dried solvents. Although formally written as seven co-ordinate complexes they may in reality be the six co-ordinate $[\text{MoX}(\text{NH})(\text{dppe})_2]\text{Cl}$ with the imido-proton hydrogen-bonded to the chloride ion, similar to the situation found in $[\text{WBr}(\text{picoline})(\text{NNH}_2)(\text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}_3)]\text{Br}$.²⁰ This hydrogen-bonding may well account for the difficulty of finding spectroscopic evidence for the imido-proton. In complex (XIV) containing the non-H-bonding tetraphenylborate anion a weak ir band at 3290 cm^{-1} , shifted to 2450 cm^{-1} on deuteration, is assigned to $\nu(\text{N-H})$. The ^{31}P nmr spectra of (XIII) in methylene chloride shows substantially one peak at 106.0 ppm relative to trimethylphosphite, consistent with a six co-ordinate species. However the presence of additional smaller peaks at 97.1 (0.17 height) and 94.9 ppm, (0.018 height) is reminiscent of the ^{31}P spectrum of $[\text{WCl}_2(\text{NNH}_2)(\text{dppe})_2]^{21}$ where the extra peaks were attributed to equilibria involving seven co-ordinate species.

The imido-complexes (XII) or (XIII) can readily be deprotonated with Et_3N in methanol to give the nitrido-complexes $[\text{MoNX}(\text{dppe})_2]$ (X and XI) in high yield. These are isolated as yellow diamagnetic crystalline substances with $\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$ assigned to ir bands at about 980 cm^{-1} . The reaction with triethylamine is reversed easily by addition of acids with reformation of imido-complexes.

Even in boiling methanol with a large excess of halogen acid there is no sign of ammonia formation from complexes (X) and (XI). Nitride intermediates have been postulated in the formation of ammonia from $[\text{Mo}(\text{N}_2)_2(\text{dppe})_2]$ and hydrogen bromide in high boiling solvents such as N-methylpyrrolidone.²² However the observation that no ammonia is formed from our $[\text{MoNX}(\text{dppe})_2]$ complexes suggests that loss of a diphosphine ligand is necessary before further protonation of the nitride ligand to ammonia can occur. This situation is analogous to the protonation of $[\text{Mo}(\text{N}_2)_2(\text{dppe})_2]$ in thf which stops at the $[\text{MoX}_2(\text{NNH}_2)_2(\text{dppe})_2]$ ²¹ stage. The presence of labile monodentate ligands such as those in $[\text{Mo}(\text{N}_2)_2(\text{PMe}_2\text{Ph})_4]$ is necessary before further protonation of the hydrazido (2-) ligand to ammonia occurs at room temperature.

The nitrido-complexes, $[\text{MoNX}(\text{dppe})_2]$, react with sodium tetraphenylborate in methanol to give pink diamagnetic complexes tentatively formulated as the imido-complexes $[\text{Mo}(\text{NH})(\text{OMe})(\text{dppe})_2]\text{BPh}_4$ (XV) and an analogous salt (XVI) is formed from sodium hexafluorophosphate.

The ir spectrum of these complexes show ir bands at about 3300 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ and their ¹H

nmr spectra show a singlet at 2.18 ppm assigned to the methoxy group. However the spectroscopic and analytical data are not sufficient to distinguish between alternative possibilities such as $[\text{MoN}(\text{HOMe})(\text{dppe})_2]\text{BPh}_4$ and we intend to identify the methanol derivatives by X-ray crystal structural methods.

Experimental

Unless stated otherwise all reactions and manipulations were carried out in dry solvents under dinitrogen. $[\text{MoCl}_4(\text{MeCN})_2]$ ²³, $[\text{MoCl}_4(\text{thf})_2]$ ²⁴, $[\text{MoCl}_3(\text{thf})_3]$ ²⁴, and $[\text{Mo}(\text{N}_2)_2(\text{dppe})_2]$ ²⁵ were prepared by established methods. Ir spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP 2000 or SP 1200 spectrophotometers as Nujol mulls. A JEOL PS-100 instrument was used to record the ¹H nmr spectra generally in CD_2Cl_2 solution with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. ³¹P nmr spectra were recorded on a JEOL PS-100 instrument operating in the Fourier-transform mode with trimethylphosphite as internal standard. ESR spectra were obtained using a Varian E3 spectrometer, and molecular weights were determined osmotically in 1, 2-dichloroethane solution on a Hitachi-Perkin Elmer 115 vapour pressure osmometer. Microanalyses for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and halogen were by Mr. and Mrs. A.G. Olney of Sussex University.

TABLE. NITRIDO AND IMIDO COMPLEXES OF MOLYBDENUM

No.	Complex	$\nu(\text{Mo}\equiv\text{N})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu(\text{NH})$ cm^{-1}	C	Analysis ^a H	N	halogen	M.W.
I	$[\text{MoNCl}_5(\text{OPPh}_3)_2]$	1038	—	55.8 (55.8)	4.2 (3.9)	1.7 (1.8)	13.5 13.7	—
II	$[\text{MoNCl}_5(\text{dpy})]$	1009	—	32.6 (32.2)	2.9 (2.7)	11.5 (11.2)	—	—
III	$[\text{Et}_3\text{N}]_2[\text{MoNCl}_5]$	1032	—	34.7 (35.1)	7.1 (7.3)	7.2 (7.6)	—	—
IV	$[\text{MoN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNMe}_2)_2]$	1019	—	23.5 (23.0)	3.9 (3.9)	11.6 (11.9)	—	524 (470)
V	$[\text{MoN}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)_2]$	1015	—	32.6 (32.5)	5.7 (5.4)	10.1 (10.1)	—	593 (554)
VI	$[\text{MoN}\{\frac{1}{2}\text{CN}(\text{CH}_2)_5\}_2]$	1013	—	36.4 (36.6)	5.3 (5.1)	9.2 (9.5)	—	620 (590)
VII	$[\text{MoNCl}_5(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$	1049	—	60.9 (61.1)	4.5 (4.3)	2.1 (2.0)	10.6 (10.1)	—
VIII	$[\text{MoNCl}_5(\text{PMePh}_2)_2]$	1046	—	52.9 (53.6)	4.5 (4.6)	2.4 (2.4)	—	—
IX	$[\text{MoN}(\text{N}_3)(\text{dppe})_2]$	972	—	65.9 (65.8)	5.1 (5.3)	5.9 (5.9)	—	—
X	$[\text{MoNCl}(\text{dppe})_2]$	977	—	65.7 (66.3)	5.0 (5.1)	1.7 (1.5)	—	903 (941)
XI	$[\text{MoNBr}(\text{dppe})_2]$	975	—	61.9 (63.2)	4.8 (4.9)	1.3 (1.4)	—	976 (988)
XII	$[\text{MoCl}_2(\text{NH})(\text{dppe})_2]$	—	—	63.6 (63.6)	4.9 (4.9)	1.5 (1.4)	7.2 (7.2)	997 (978)
XIII	$[\text{MoBr}_2(\text{NH})(\text{dppe})_2]$	—	—	58.5 (58.5)	4.7 (4.6)	1.5 (1.3)	—	—
XIV	$[\text{MoBr}(\text{NH})(\text{dppe})_2]\text{BPh}_4$	—	3350	66.9 (66.4)	5.3 (5.0)	1.1 (1.0)	5.3 (5.8)	—
XV	$[\text{Mo}(\text{NH})(\text{OMe})(\text{dppe})_2]\text{BPh}_4^b$	—	3345	69.7 (69.8)	5.7 (5.5)	1.1 (1.0)	4.2 ^c (5.2)	—
XVI	$[\text{Mo}(\text{NH})(\text{OMe})(\text{dppe})_2]\text{PF}_6^b$	—	3340	55.5 (56.2)	4. (4.4)	1.3 (1.2)	—	—

^a Calculated values in parenthesis

^b With one mole CH_2Cl_2 of crystallisation

^c Cl analysis—0% Br found.

The Roman numerals correspond to those used in Table I. *Trichloro (nitrido) bis (triphenylphosphine) oxide molybdenum (VI)*, (I).— To a stirred suspension of tetrachlorobis (tetrahydrofuran)-molybdenum (IV) (1.9g, 0.005 mole) in dry tetrahydrofuran (40ml) was added trimethylsilyl azide (0.63g, 0.0055 mole) dropwise. Dinitrogen was evolved rapidly to give a clear orange red solution which was evaporated at 10^{-2} mm Hg to an orange-red oil (A). Addition of triphenylphosphine oxide (3.1g, 0.011 mole) to a benzene solution of (A) (50ml) caused the product to crystalline as analytically pure pale yellow plates. (2.9g, 70%).

Trichloro (nitrido) (dipyridyl) molybdenum (VI), (II), was prepared analogously to (I) in 62% yield by addition of 1.1 equivalents of dipyridyl to an acetonitrile solution of (A).

Tetraethylammonium Pentachloro (nitrido) molybdenum (VI), (III).— Trimethylsilyl azide (0.63g, 0.0055 mole) was added to a stirred suspension of tetrachlorobis (tetrahydrofuran) molybdenum (V) (1.9g, 0.005 mole) in dichloromethane (40ml). Addition of dried tetraethylammonium chloride (2.5g, 0.015 mole) to the resulting clear orange-red solution caused the product to precipitate as an analytically pure yellow solid in 53% yield.

Nitridotris (diethyldithiocarbamate) molybdenum (VI), (V).— *Method 1* :- 3.3 equivalents of trimethylsilyl diethyldithiocarbamate were added to a dichloromethane solution of (A) prepared as for complex (III). The resulting brown-yellow solution was evaporated to low volume and the product precipitated as a yellow solid by addition of methanol. It crystallised as pale yellow prisms from dichloromethane-diethyl ether (58% yield).

Method 2 :- Chlorotris (diethyldithiocarbamate) molybdenum (IV)²⁶ (2.0g, 0.0034 mole) in methyl cyanide (40ml) was heated under reflux with sodium azide (1.0g, 0.015 mole) for 0.5h. The resulting orange-red solution was evaporated to near dryness and the complex precipitated with methanol (40ml), washed with water, methanol and diethyl ether and recrystallised from dichloromethane-diethyl ether (1.3g, 69.2%).

Complexes (IV) and (VI) were prepared analogously using Method 2 above with the appropriate molybdenum (IV) precursor in yields of 76% and 71% respectively.

Dichloro (nitrido) bis (triphenylphosphine) molybdenum (V), (VII).— Three equivalents of triphenylphosphine were added to a dichloromethane solution of (A) prepared as for complex (III). The product slowly crystallised from solution as a yellow analytically pure solid in about 60% yield.

Dichloro (nitrido) bis (methylphenylphosphine) molybdenum (V), (VIII).— Trimethylsilyl azide (0.6g, 0.005 mole) and trichlorotris- (tetrahydrofuran) molybdenum (III) (2.1 g, 0.005 mole) were heated under reflux in tetrahydrofuran (40ml) for 0.5h.

Methylphenylphosphine (3.0g, 0.015 mole) was added, the solution stirred for 0.5h, and evaporated to ca. 5ml at 10^{-2} mm Hg. The product was precipitated by the addition of propan-2-ol (25ml) and recrystallised as yellow prisms from dichloromethane-hexane.

Azido (nitrido) bis [bis (diphenylphosphino) ethane] molybdenum (IV), (IX).— Trimethylsilylazide (1.3g, 0.011 mole) and bis (dinitrogen)-bis [bis (diphenylphosphino) ethane] molybdenum (0) (4.0g, 0.0342 mole) were heated under reflux in tetrahydrofuran (40ml) for 0.5h. The resulting reddish-brown solution was evaporated to near dryness at 10^{-2} mm Hg and diethyl ether (40ml) added, precipitating the product as a pale yellow solid (1.9g, 47.5%). This can be filtered off in air and is sufficiently pure for subsequent reactions. Alternatively the reaction can be carried out in methyl cyanide whereupon complex (IX) crystallises out on cooling in an analytically pure state.

Dichloro (imido) bis [bis (diphenylphosphino) ethane] molybdenum (IV), (XII).— Azidonitridobis [bis (diphenylphosphino) ethane] molybdenum (IV), (0.5g), was suspended in reagent grade methanol (20ml) and three drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid added. There was an immediate colour change to pink and the product crystallised from the solution as red-pink needles on standing. (0.43g, 83%).

Complex (XIII) was prepared analogously in 84% yield using concentrated hydrobromic acid.

Chloro (nitrido) bis [bis (diphenylphosphino) ethane] molybdenum (IV), (X).— Complex (XIII), (0.5g), was suspended in reagent grade methyl cyanide (20ml) and triethylamine (0.5ml) added. The pink colour of the imido-complex was immediately discharged and the product crystallised from solution as lemon-yellow plates (0.35g, 70%).

Complex (XI) was prepared analogously starting with complex (XIII).

Bromo (imido) bis [bis (diphenylphosphino) ethane] molybdenum (IV) tetraphenylborate, (XIV).— Complex (XIII), (0.4g), was suspended in reagent grade methanol (40ml) and sodium tetraphenylborate (0.4g) added. The product precipitated as a lilac solid after 0.5h of stirring and was recrystallised from dichloromethane-methyl ether as pale violet needles.

Reaction of methanol with complexes (X) or (XI).— Complexes (X) or (XI), (0.5g), were suspended in reagent grade methanol (40ml) and stirred for 0.5h with sodium tetraphenylborate (0.3g). The product, possibly imidomethoxybis [bis (diphenylphosphino) ethane] molybdenum (IV) tetraphenylborate (XV), precipitated as a pale orange solid. It recrystallised as pink needles from dichloromethane-diethyl ether. The hexafluoroborate (XVI) was prepared analogously.

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